

Table S1. (a) Questions administered to lactose-intolerant consumers and possible relative answers.

Questionnaire administered to lactose-intolerant consumers	
Question	Answers
Are you lactose intolerant?	Yes
	I am a parent or guardian of a lactose intolerant minor
How did you find out you are lactose intolerant?	No
	Diagnosed by breath test and/or specific genetic test
	Auto-diagnosis
How long have you known you are lactose intolerant?	Not-validated tests (e.g. Vega-Test, Cito-Test)
	Since birth
	Less than 1 year
	1-3 years
What is your gender?	More than 3 years
	Male
	Female
What is your age?	Less than 18 years
	18-24 years
	25-34 years
	35-44 years
	45-54 years
	More than 55 years
What is your occupation?	Abruzzo
	Basilicata
	Calabria
	Employee
	Student
Do you consume naturally lactose-free cheeses and/or "delactosed" cheeses?	Non-resident student
	Stay-at-home
	Retired
	Yes, both
	Yes, only naturally lactose-free cheeses
Which are the PDO cheeses that you buy the most? Choose a maximum of three options.	Yes, only "delactosed" cheeses
	Rarely
	Never
	Grana Padano and Parmigiano Reggiano long-aged (30-36 months)
	Grana Padano and Parmigiano Reggiano (any ageing)
	Gorgonzola
What is your knowledge about the difference between naturally lactose-free cheeses and "delactosed" cheeses?	Emmentaler
	Pecorino
	Fontina
	Scarce
	Sufficient
How often do you understand if PDO cheese is naturally lactose-free from its label?	Good
	Excellent
	Rarely
Do you think a list of naturally lactose-free cheeses would be useful to consult?	Sometimes
	Always
	Not at all
Do you think a list of naturally lactose-free cheeses would be useful to consult?	Yes, but I wouldn't use it
	Yes, it could be useful
	Yes, it is necessary

(b) Questions administered to professionals of nutrition and possible relative answers

Questionnaire administered to professionals of nutrition	
Question	Answers
What is your occupation?	Medical dietitians (physician nutrition specialist)
	Nutritionists (enrolled in the order of biologists)
	Dietitians (enrolled in the order of dietitians)
How long have you been exercising your professional activity?	0-3 years
	4-10 years
	More than 10 years
Which are the Italian regions you work in?	Abruzzo
	Basilicata
	Calabria
	Campania
	Emilia Romagna
	Friuli-Venezia Giulia
	Lazio
	Liguria
	Lombardia
	Marche
	Molise
	Piemonte
	Puglia
	Sardegna
	Sicilia
	Toscana
Trentino-Alto Adige	
Umbria	
Valle d'Aosta	
Veneto	
How many are your patients in total? Indicate the numer in the year 2019.	Less than 50
	51-100
	101-200
	More than 200
How many are your lactose-intolerant patients? Indicate the numer in the year 2019.	Less than 25
	26-50
	51-100
What is your knowledge about lactose intolerance topic?	Scarce
	Sufficient
	Good
	Excellent, acquired thanks to certified training courses
Which test did your lactose intolerant patients are mainly diagnosed by when you first visited them?	H2 Lactose Breath test
	LCT C/T-13910 Genetic test
	Both above-mentioned tests
	Auto-diagnosis
	Not-validated tests (e.g. Vega-Test, Cito-Test)
How much clarity do you think there is about the topic "lactose intolerance and naturally lactose-free cheeses"?	Scarce
	Sufficient
	Good
	Excellent
Which are the naturally lactose-free PDO cheese that you advise to your lactose intolerant patients the most? Choose a maximum of three options.	Grana Padano and Parmigiano Reggiano long-aged (30-36 months)
	Grana padano and Parmigiano Reggiano (any ageing)
	Gorgonzola
	Emmentaler
	Pecorino
Do you think the nowadays labeling policy for naturally lactose-free PDO cheeses to be satisfying?	Fontina
	Scarce
	Sufficient
Do you think a table of naturally lactose-free cheeses would be useful to distribute to your lactose intolerant patients?	Good
	Not at all
	Yes, but I wouldn't use it
	Yes, it could be useful
Do you know about the Italian lactose-intolerant patients' association, AII (Associazione Italiana Latto-Intolleranti)?	Yes, it is necessary
	No
	I have heard of it
How did you learn about the Association?	Yes
	Personal research on Google
	Event (stands, trade fairs, conventionals)
	Social media (Facebook, Instagram)
	Word-of-mouth